

A Controlled Perturbation Algorithm for Saddle Point Escape of Generic Non-convex Optimization Problems: Deterministic Optimization Problems (Algorithms and Experiments)

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Abstract

We introduce the Controlled Perturbation Algorithm (CPA) for escaping saddle points in generic *deterministic* non-convex optimization problems. CPA uses two gradient evaluations per iteration, which is a constant factor ($2\times$) more than GD, but still linear in the cost of a single gradient call. The key idea is to use two adaptive perturbations per coordinate, evaluate their directional derivatives, and deterministically select a descent direction – all without computing second or higher order derivatives. There are two possibilities: 1. CPA could be used as an independent tool to assist escape of saddle points and, in particular, may escape saddle points more efficiently than Perturbed Gradient Descent (PGD).; 2. CPA could be a stand-alone algorithm for the whole optimization problem. We also define the Non-Descent Direction Approximation (NDDA) index as a cheap heuristic indicator of proximity to a local minimum for *deterministic optimization problems only*.

1 Background and motivation

Non-convex optimization lies at the heart of modern machine learning, signal processing, robotics, and many scientific computing applications. The loss landscapes in these domains are typically rugged, containing a multitude of critical points – local minima, local maxima, and saddle points. While local minima are desirable, saddle points can severely impede the convergence of first-order methods such as gradient descent (GD). At a strict saddle point, the gradient is zero but the Hessian possesses at least one negative eigenvalue, making it an unstable equilibrium. Near such points, GD stalls because it lacks directional information to descend further.

Classical strategies to escape saddle points include adding random noise (perturbed gradient descent, or PGD), using momentum, or leveraging second-order curvature information (e.g., trust-region methods, negative curvature search). Among these, PGD has gained popularity due to its simplicity and theoretical guarantees: by occasionally injecting isotropic Gaussian noise, it escapes strict saddles with high probability and converges to second-order stationary points. However, PGD has notable limitations:

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- **Inefficiency of random kicks:** The perturbation direction is purely random. Many kicks may be wasted before a descent direction is accidentally found.
- **Difficulty with non-strict saddles:** When the Hessian is positive semi-definite (some eigenvalues zero), PGD often fails because there is no negative curvature to exploit; the algorithm may wander on a plateau for an extremely long time.
- **Lack of a cheap convergence indicator:** Standard stopping criteria rely on gradient norm, which does not distinguish between saddles and minima. Reliable detection of minima often requires Hessian information, which is computationally prohibitive in high dimensions.

These shortcomings motivate the need for a (semi-)deterministic, curvature-agnostic method that can (i) reliably identify a descent direction near saddles without relying on random chance, (ii) handle both strict and non-strict saddles, and (iii) provide an inexpensive, real-time measure of how close the iterate is to a local minimum.

This preprint serves as providing the experimental results in Sections 5 and 6 for CPA introduced in [1] for *deterministic optimization problems* only. For *probabilistic* experiments, particularly on 3GCPA and the hybrid version of 3GCPA-Adam, are in progress. The preliminary results in this directions seem positive, but details would be published after more confirmation.

2 Heuristic physical picture for Controlled Perturbation Algorithm for *deterministic optimization problems*

We first consider *deterministic optimization problems*. Suppose we would like to minimize a function $E(\theta)$, with dimension of θ being d . Suppose the system is at $\theta = \theta_0$. The idea of the Controlled Perturbation Algorithm is, for any i -th coordinate, an ε_i is chosen randomly. Gradient would then be computed at perturbed point $\theta_0 + \varepsilon$, whose sign on i -th coordinate would reflect whether the function is ascent or descent direction along the move ε_i in this direction. If it is descent, this direction would be our desired move. On the other hand, if the direction is ascent, we may consider its opposite direction. If this opposite direction is a descent one, this would be the desired direction. But if this direction is also ascent, it would be an indicator that the system may have a high chance in local minimum along this i -th coordinate. Therefore, we do not change the coordinate in this direction.

Making use of the above idea, we propose the Non-Descent Direction Approximation (NDDA) Index on the ratio of non-descent directions in both forward and backward probes in *deterministic optimization problems* (For *probabilistic optimization problems*, like machine learning, the generalization to that cases remain an open question). In local minimum, this index would be expected to be close to 1.

A rigorous saddle point escape rate for the Controlled Perturbation Algorithm (CPA) is beyond the scope of this work. Nevertheless, we offer a heuristic argument for why its

escape efficiency should be at least competitive with perturbed gradient descent (PGD) [5]. In PGD, a random perturbation is added uniformly in all directions to help the iterates leave saddle points. While this suffices to guarantee polynomial-time escape, a large fraction of the random directions may not correspond to descent directions in the local geometry, potentially requiring many attempts. In contrast, CPA uses an additional gradient evaluation to bias the perturbation toward directions of steepest descent. Therefore, we expect that CPA may waste fewer iterations on non-descent perturbations, and under similar smoothness conditions its escape efficiency may be at least as good as that of PGD. A formal Proof, or disproof, of this intuition is an interesting direction for future work.

Regarding the application of CPA, we currently have two proposals: 1. using them only once the system reaches a stationary point where the gradient vanishes. Specifically, CPA is applied to escape the stationary point, with, for *deterministic optimization problems*, the NDDA index serving as an indicator of whether a descent direction is present; after escape, the optimizer can switch to a traditional algorithm such as Adam or standard gradient descent. In this article, we only focus on the performance of CPA and PGD due to their similar nature. For comparison with other saddle point escape optimizers, it would be left for future investigation. 2. as a standalone optimizer for the whole optimization processes.

3 Controlled Perturbation Algorithm (CPA) for *deterministic optimization problems*

The following pseudocode describes the algorithm. Note that the computational cost is $O(d)$ per iteration, where d is the number of parameters (degrees of freedom).

Algorithm 1 Controlled Perturbation Algorithm (CPA)

Require: Objective function $E(\theta)$, $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d$; initial parameters θ_0 ; amplification factor $\alpha \in [1.1, 2.0]$ (default 1.3); noise scale σ (or per-coordinate σ_i); max iterations K .

Ensure: θ_{final}

- 1: **for** $t = 0, \dots, K - 1$ **do**
- 2: Sample $\varepsilon_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \text{diag}(\sigma_i^2))$ for each coordinate i .
- 3: Compute $I_{1,i} = \varepsilon_i \frac{\partial E}{\partial \theta_i} \Big|_{\theta_0 + \varepsilon}$ for every i .
- 4: Obtain ε'_i :

$$\varepsilon'_i = \begin{cases} \alpha \varepsilon_i & \text{if } I_{1,i} < 0 \\ -\varepsilon_i & \text{if } I_{1,i} > 0 \end{cases}$$

- 5: Compute the second index at $\theta_0 + \varepsilon'$:

$$I_{2,i} = \varepsilon'_i \frac{\partial E}{\partial \theta_i} \Big|_{\theta_0 + \varepsilon'}$$

- 6: **if** $I_{2,i} < 0$ **then**
 - 7: $\theta_{0,i} \leftarrow \theta_{0,i} + \varepsilon'_i$ ▷ Descent found along ε'
 - 8: **else if** $I_{1,i} < 0$ and $I_{2,i} > 0$ **then**
 - 9: $\theta_{0,i} \leftarrow \theta_{0,i} + \varepsilon_i$ ▷ Descent found only along original ε
 - 10: **else if** $I_{1,i} > 0$ and $I_{2,i} > 0$ **then**
 - 11: $\theta_{0,i} \leftarrow \theta_{0,i}$ ▷ No descent direction in this coordinate
 - 12: **end if**
 - 13: **end for**
 - 14: **return** θ_{final}
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Remark: The case $I_{1,i} = 0$ or $I_{2,i} = 0$ is extremely unlikely with random perturbations and continuous gradients; in practice we treat zero as non-descent (no update).

4 Non-Descent Direction Approximation (NDDA) Index for *deterministic optimization problems*

For *deterministic optimization problems*, where there is no intrinsic noise, the NDDA index is a heuristic indicator of how many coordinates behave like they are at a local minimum. It is computed by the same two perturbations but without performing any parameter update.

It has to be reminded that, in *probabilistic cases*, like most machine learning cases, the samples may have probabilistic fluctuation, which makes the index not close to 1 even if local minimum is achieved.

Algorithm 2 NDDA Index

Require: Objective function $E(\theta)$, $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^d$; current parameters θ_0 ; amplification factor α ; noise scale σ .

Ensure: NDDA $\in [0, 1]$

- 1: Sample $\varepsilon_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \text{diag}(\sigma_i^2))$.
 - 2: Compute $I_{1,i} = \varepsilon_i \left. \frac{\partial E}{\partial \theta_i} \right|_{\theta_0 + \varepsilon}$.
 - 3: Obtain ε'_i as in CPA.
 - 4: Compute $I_{2,i} = \varepsilon'_i \left. \frac{\partial E}{\partial \theta_i} \right|_{\theta_0 + \varepsilon'}$.
 - 5: NDDA = $\frac{\#\{i | I_{1,i} \geq 0 \text{ and } I_{2,i} \geq 0\}}{d}$
 - 6: **return** NDDA
-

For *deterministic optimization problems*, when NDDA ≈ 1 , the algorithm suggests that for most coordinates neither perturbation direction leads to a descent – this is consistent with being near a local minimum (or a very flat region). Conversely, low NDDA values indicate that many coordinates still have a detectable descent direction, which typically occurs near saddle points or on slopes.

Remark on perturbation magnitude choices

1. Diminishing parameters: start with a relatively large σ to escape saddles quickly, then decrease it gradually to fine-tune near a minimum.
2. Data-driven scaling: for neural networks, one can pass a batch of data through the model, compute the mean and standard deviation of each layer’s output, and set σ_i proportional to those statistics to keep perturbations in a natural range.

5 Experiment - Method 1: Use Gradient Descent (GD) then switch to Perturbed Gradient Descent (PGD) or Controlled Perturbation Algorithm (CPA), respectively, at Saddle Point to Check Performance

We list the results of 5 representative experiments on high-dimensional non-convex problems: First applying GD, then switch to PGD or CPA, respectively, to compare performance.

The optimizers would be switched to CPA or PGD, respectively, when GD is used and the maximum component-wise gradient is below a small threshold. The threshold is set to be the same for both CPA and PGD.

For details on the hyper-parameter settings, please refer to the attached source codes where the exact values used in the experiments are specified.

5.1 Experiment 1: Ackley Function

The objective function is:

$$f(x) = 20 + e - \exp\left(\frac{1}{1000} \sum_{i=1}^{1000} \cos(2\pi x_i)\right) - 20 \exp\left(\sqrt{\frac{1}{1000} \sum_{i=1}^{1000} x_i^2}\right)$$

Initial $x_i \sim 4 + \mathcal{N}(0, 0.01)$. Training for 80000 epochs.
The perturbations are chosen as $\varepsilon_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.001)$

(a) Function value of Ackley Function.

(b) NDDA of Ackley Function.

(c) Minimum Eigenvalue of the Hessian on Ackley Function.

Figure 1: The training results of Ackley Function with GD+CPA and GD+PGD.

5.2 Experiment 2: Matrix Factorization

Choose a matrix $X = Q_1 \lambda Q_2$ with Q_1 (dimension = 1000×1000), Q_2 (dimension 500×500) random orthogonal matrices, λ is a diagonal matrix containing $i^{1.5}$ for $i = 1, \dots, 69$.

We consider the task of factorizing X into U (1000×50) and V (50×500), with loss $\|X - UV\|_2$.

Initial U, V are all-ones, learning rate and σ linearly decreases from 0.025 to 0.0005. The number of epochs is 100000.

(a) Loss comparison on matrix factorization.

(b) NDDA indices for matrix factorization.

Figure 2: The training results of Matrix Factorization with GD+CPA and GD+PGD.

5.3 Experiment 3: Rastrigin Function

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=1}^{100} (x_i^2 - 10 \cos(2\pi x_i))$$

First train with PGD (standard deviation 0.01, learning rate 0.02). Then continue with CPA for 1000 epochs, linearly decreasing σ from 0.1 to 0.001.

Figure 3: The training results of Rastrigin Function with GD+CPA and GD+PGD.

5.4 Experiment 4: Spin Glass (Traditional)

The objective function to be minimized is

$$E = \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq N=1000} J_{ij} s_i s_j, \quad J_{ij} \sim \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$$

Continuous variables (s_i), initial condition $0.4 \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$.

Figure 4: The training results of spin glass model (traditional) with GD+CPA and GD+PGD.

5.5 Experiment 5: Spin Glass with Artificial Uneven Coupling

The objective function in this case has the same functional form as the traditional spin glass model but but with block-dependent coupling strengths:

$$J_{ij} \sim \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \mathcal{N}(0, 1) & 1 \leq i < j \leq 500 \\ \frac{3}{\sqrt{N}} \mathcal{N}(0, 1) & 1 \leq i < 500 \leq j \leq 1000 \\ \frac{5}{\sqrt{N}} \mathcal{N}(0, 1) & 500 \leq i < j \leq 1000 \end{cases}$$

Initial condition $0.4 \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$.

The perturbations are chosen as $\varepsilon_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.01)$

(a) Energy on spin glass with artificial uneven coupling.

(b) NDDA on spin glass with artificial uneven coupling.

(c) Minimum Eigenvalue of the Hessian on spin glass with artificial uneven coupling.

Figure 5: The training results of Spin Glass with Artificial Uneven Coupling with GD+CPA and GD+PGD.

5.6 Interpretation of results

In all five experiments, CPA performs at least as well as PGD for escaping saddle points when GD achieves stationary points, and often reaches a lower final loss. The NDDA index consistently rises towards 1 when CPA is applied, supporting the heuristic that a high NDDA value correlates with being close to a local minimum, except for the experiment 2 where the index only achieves 0.8. In experiment 2, the matrix factorization has a large degeneracy as U and V could be replaced by UR and $R^{-1}V$, where R is an invertible matrix without affecting their product. Therefore, it would be an interesting research direction to investigate if such degeneracy would lead to a lower NDDA index.

6 Experiment - Method 2: Use Gradient Descent (GD), Perturbed Gradient Descent (PGD) and Controlled Perturbation Algorithm (CPA) as Standalone Optimizers

We list the results of the above 5 experiments with GD, PGD and CPA as the standalone optimizers, which includes the region where the gradient is non-zero.

For details on the hyper-parameter settings (which are the same as in Section 5), please refer to the attached source codes where the exact values used in the experiments are specified.

6.1 Experiment 1: Ackley Function

The function is the same as Subsection 5.1.

(a) Function value of Ackley Function.

(b) NDDA of Ackley Function.

(c) Minimum Eigenvalue of the Hessian on Ackley Function.

Figure 6: The training results of Ackley Function with GD, PGD and CPA as the standalone optimizers.

6.2 Experiment 2: Matrix Factorization

The function is the same as Subsection 5.2.

(a) Loss comparison on matrix factorization.

(b) NDDA indices for matrix factorization.

Figure 7: The training results of Matrix Factorization with GD, PGD and CPA as the standalone optimizers.

6.3 Experiment 3: Rastrigin Function

The function is the same as Subsection 5.3.

(a) Loss of Rastrigin Function.

(b) NDDA on Rastrigin Function.

(c) Minimum Eigenvalue of the Hessian on Rastrigin Function.

Figure 8: The training results of Rastrigin Function with GD, PGD and CPA as the standalone optimizers.

6.4 Experiment 4: Spin Glass (Traditional)

The function is the same as Subsection 5.4.

(a) Energy on traditional spin glass

(b) NDDA on traditional spin glass.

(c) Minimum Eigenvalue of the Hessian on traditional spin glass.

(d) Ratio of non-negative eigenvalues on traditional spin glass.

Figure 9: The training results of spin glass model with GD, PGD and CPA as the standalone optimizers.

6.5 Experiment 5: Spin Glass with Artificial Uneven Coupling

The function is the same as Subsection 5.5.

(a) Energy on spin glass with artificial uneven coupling

(b) NDDA on spin glass with artificial uneven coupling.

(c) Minimum Eigenvalue of the Hessian on spin glass with artificial even coupling.

Figure 10: The training results of spin glass with artificial uneven coupling with GD, PGD and CPA as the standalone optimizers.

6.6 Conclusion of these second set of experiment

In this section, we could see that CPA could act as a standalone optimizer on itself. It is worth noting that compared with section 5, with gradient as base optimizer and CPA is only used when the gradient is small, CPA alone converges much faster than the hybrid case.

Note to the reader

The author’s background is in physics, not in formal optimization theory. Consequently, this work prioritizes a clear physical picture – treating the loss landscape as an energy landscape and using controlled perturbations to “feel” the local curvature – over mathematical rigor. The algorithm and the NDDA index are presented as *heuristic tools*. Formal guarantees, convergence rates, and detailed comparisons with state-of-the-art optimizers, other than PGD, are left for future work.

The source code is provided with this preprint. If any errors are discovered, the author would appreciate being notified by email at khcheng920911@gmail.com .

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